

STRATEGIES AND MEDIA OF ONLINE LEARNING DURING THE PANDEMIC

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WHAT IS ONLINE LEARNING?

- Online learning is learning that utilizes multimedia technology, video, virtual classes, animated online text, voice messages, e-mail, conference calls, and online video streaming.

LEARNING MATERIALS

Material can be in the form of text, images, video and sound. The learning objective is to become a more creative, critical thinker and a higher quality and more flexible reader.

The assignments given began to vary from making videos on the YouTube channel, doing test questions on Google Form. The learning system through video conferencing can be done for the effectiveness of learning and so that it is not boring for students. However, the use of an adequate internet network is necessary for conducting video conferencing)

STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE ONLINE LEARNING

- Know the technology
- Expect the unexpected
- Create and maintain strong presence
- Set clear expectation of the course
- Establish time management
- Promote reflection and communication
- Check content and applications

CHOOSING DIGITAL TOOLS FOR ONLINE LEARNING

- Accessibility
- Capacity
- Durability
- Facillity
- Practically

LEARNING MEDIA

- Learning media that can be used Google Classroom, Google form, and Youtube

GOOGLE CLASSROOM

Ferina Haryanti
5 Nov 2020 (Diedit pada 18 Nov 20...)

Good Morning Students. Hari ini adalah pertemuan pertama kita di kelas ini. Materi kita hari ini adalah tentang greeting (salam) dan Introduction (perkenalan).

1 komentar kelas

opening (greeting students)

Bahasa Inggris kelas IV A

Material about greeting and introduction.

Ferina Haryanti • 5 Nov 2020 (Diedit 18 Nov 2020)

Baca dan tonton video materi tersebut. Pelajari materi ini di rumah bersama orangtua atau saudara kalian.

- Greeting (salam).png
Gambar
- Introduction (perkenala...
Gambar
- Pembelajaran Materi Ba...
Video YouTube 6 menit

Komentar kelas

Tambahkan komentar kelas...

Learning materials

Bahasa Inggris kelas IV A

Petunjuk Tugas siswa

Quiz meeting 1

Ferina Haryanti • 5 Nov 2020 (Diedit 5 Nov 2020)

100 poin

Please answer the questions below carefully.
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSepizR2Or_nvfx4t4Ir15fgBvAyrxiM1EXmFh3PI0wGnUYWtQ/view?form?vc=0&c=0&w=1&flr=0

Komentar kelas

Tambahkan komentar kelas...

Assessment (measuring student knowledge)

GOOGLE CLASSROOM

A screenshot of a Google Classroom post. At the top left is a profile picture of a woman, followed by the name "Ferina Haryanti" and the date "5 Nov 2020 (Diedit 19 Nov 2020)". To the right of the name is a three-dot menu icon. The main text of the post reads: "kesimpulan dari pembelajaran kita hari adalah greeting adalah sebuah ungkapan yang biasanya digunakan oleh seseorang untuk melakukan tegur sapa atau salam dengan orang lain. Sedangkan introduction adalah ungkapan/ekspresi yang digunakan untuk perkenalan atau memperkenalkan diri dalam bahasa Inggris. Perkenalan ada dua macam, yaitu memperkenalkan diri sendiri dan memperkenalkan orang lain." At the bottom left is another profile picture, and to its right is a text input field with the placeholder "Tambahkan komentar kelas..." and a right-pointing arrow icon.

conclusion from learning

A screenshot of a Google Classroom class page. At the top, it says "Bahasa Inggris kelas IV A" with a hamburger menu icon on the left and a gear icon on the right. Below this are three tabs: "Forum" (highlighted in green), "Tugas Kelas", and "Anggota". The main header area is green and contains the text "Bahasa Inggris kelas IV A" and "1". Below this is the "Kode kelas" "kad7njx" with a QR code icon. To the right of the code are the options "Pilih tema" and "Upload foto". Below the header is a post by "Ferina Haryanti" dated "19 Nov 2020". The post text says: "Untuk pelajaran bahasa Inggris hari ini ibu cukupkan sampai disini. Minggu depan kita lanjutkan lagi ke materi selanjutnya. Good morning. See you at the next meeting, students." At the bottom left is a profile picture, and to its right is a text input field with the placeholder "Tambahkan komentar kelas..." and a right-pointing arrow icon.

Closing

**THANK YOU FOR YOUR
ATTENTION**